

GREAT PROBLEM EXAMPLES AND THEIR SOLUTIONS

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Abstract: This is a that covers almost all areas of mathematics ,through which many theorems and proofs of inequalities arise.

Keywords: induction, mathematick induction, inequality, incomplete induction, complete induktion

Аннотация: Это тема , охватываюуая почти все облости математики ,благодаря которой возникает множество теорема и доказательство неравенств.

Ключевые слова : индуксия , математическая индуксия, неравенство ,неполная индуксия ,полная индуксия.

Problem 1. Let k be a positive integer. Find all positive integers n such that $3^n \mid 2^n - 1$

Solution. $2 \mid n$ otherwise $2^n - 1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$. If $n = 2m$, we should have

$$v_3(4^m - 1) = v_3(m) + 1 \geq k,$$

$m = 3k - 1s$ for some $s \in \mathbb{N}$.

Problem 2. Let a, n be two positive integers and let p be an odd prime number such that

$$a^p \equiv 1 \pmod{p^n}.$$

Prove that

$$a \equiv 1 \pmod{p^{n-1}}.$$

Solution. By Fermat, $a \equiv a^p \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$, so v

$$v_p(a-1) = v_p(a^p - 1) - 1 \geq n - 1$$

Problem 3. Show that the only positive integer value of a for which $4(a^n + 1)$ is a perfect cube for all positive integers n , is 1,

Solution. If $a > 1$, $a^2 + 1$ is not a power of 2 (because it is > 2 and either 1 or 2 modulo 4). Choose some odd prime $p \mid a^2 + 1$. Now, take some $n = 2m$ with odd m and notice that $v_p(4(a^n + 1)) = v_p(a^2 + 1) + v_p(m)$ but $v_p(m)$ can be anything we want modulo 3.

Problem 4. Let $k > 1$ be an integer. Show that there exists infinitely many positive integers n such that

$$n \mid 1^n + 2^n + 3^n \dots + k^n$$

Solution. If $1 + k$ is not a power of 2, choose an odd prime $p \mid 1 + k$ and take $n = p^m$. Then, for each j not divisible by p , we have

$$v_p (j^n + (k + 1 - j)^n) = v_p (k + 1) + v_p (n) \geq m + 1.$$

Also, if $p \mid j$ (and, thereby, $p \mid k+1-j$), then $n \mid p^m \mid j^n$ so the sum in question is divisible by $p^m = n$. If $1+k$ is a power of 2, then take an odd prime divisor p of k and repeat the above argument with $k-1$ instead of k (the last term k^n is, obviously, not a problem)

Problem 5. Let p be a prime number, and a and n positive integer. Prove that if

$$2^p + 3^p = a^n.$$

then $n = 1$.

Solution. $2^2 + 3^2 = 13$, so assume that p is odd. Then $2^p + 3^p \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$, so it cannot be a square. But $v_5 (2^p + 3^p) = 1 + v_5 (p) \leq 2$.

Problem 6. Find all positive integers n for which there exist positive integers x, y and k such that $\gcd(x, y) = 1, k > 1$ and

$$3^n = x^k + y^k$$

Solution. k must be odd since the sum of 2 squares is divisible by 3 only if both squares are. If $p \mid x + y$, then p is odd and $v_p (3^n) = v_p (x^k + y^k) = v_p (k) + v_p (x + y)$, which means that $p = 3$, so $x + y = 3^m$ and $n = v_3 (k) + m$. Now it is just cases. a) $m > 1$. Then $v_3 (k) \leq k-2$ for all $k > 1$, and $M = \max(x, y) \geq 5$ so

$$x^k + y^k \geq M^k > \frac{1}{2} 3^{m+k-1} > 3^m 5^{k-2} \geq 3^{m+k-2} \geq 3^{m+v_3(k)} = 3^n,$$

which gives an immediate contradiction. b) $m = 1$. Then $x = 1, y = 2$ (or vice versa) and we get $3^{1+v_3(k)} = 1 + 2^k$, meaning $k \leq 2(1 + v_3(k))$ whence $v_3(k) = 1$, so $n = 2$ giving the only solution.

$$3^2 = 1^3 + 2^3$$

Problem 7. Let x, y, p, n, k be positive integers such that n is odd and p is a prime. Prove that if $x^k + y^k = p^n$, then n is a power of p .

Solution. $x + y \mid x^k + y^k = p^n$, so $x + y = p^m$. Now divide x and y by the highest power of p they contain (it has to be the same). This may change k and m but not n in our condition. Then use the LTE to get $m + v_p(n) = k$, so $x^k + y^k = (x + y) p^{v_p(n)}$. If $n \neq p^{v_p(n)}$, we get $n \geq 2p^{v_p(n)} \geq 2$, so

$$M^n < x^k + y^k \leq \frac{n}{2}(x + y) \leq nM$$

and $M < n^{\frac{1}{n-1}}$ which is less than 2 for odd $n \geq 3$ but the case $M = 1$ is impossible.

Problem 8. Let m, n, b be three positive integers with $m \neq n$ and $b > 1$. Show that if prime divisors of the numbers $b^n - 1$ and $b^m - 1$ be the same, then $b + 1$ is a perfect power of 2.

Solution. I failed to find a way to use the LTE here. The way I solved it is as follows. Let $u = \gcd(m, n)$. Then $b^u - 1$ and $b^{2u} - 1$ have the same prime divisors (this uses the proof of the principle I mentioned rather than the statement itself: when you repeat going from m, n to $m - n, n$, you stop when you get two equal numbers). But then each prime dividing $b^u + 1$ has to divide $b^u - 1$ whence $b^u + 1$ is a power of 2. If u were even, the remainder of the LHS modulo 4 would be 2, so u is odd. Then $b + 1 \mid b^u + 1$ and must be a power of 2 too.

References:

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